

Innovative Organic Fruit Breeding and Uses

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Abstract	This deliverable summarizes the outcomes of a survey addressed to a large panel of European stakeholders carried out in the framework of the 'InnOBreed' project to get a better understanding of the current fruit tree organic breeding needs and lack of knowledge across Europe. The survey aimed to collect data (126 responses from 11 countries) on currently used methods, materials, and tools of breeding/testing, major traits focused on today and traits that may become more important in the future in breeding/testing, and areas of needs, unresolved problems, and innovative solutions in fruit breeding/testing and fruit tree propagation in nurseries, with a focus on pip fruits (apple, pear) and stone fruits (apricot, cherry, peach).
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Executive summary

Several areas of problems and needs appeared across organic fruit breeding, variety testing, and plant propagation in nurseries. Due firstly to the fact that fruit trees are perennial plants submitted to many periods (at least 10 to 20 years) of biotic and abiotic stress risks and secondly due to some restrictions in organic production, also concerning breeding, variety testing, and fruit propagation in nurseries, these are facing **more constraints and pressures**:

- **No mineral fertilizers, no herbicides.** This leads to slower growth of the trees and all processes take longer. Especially for young trees, weed management is crucial to limit competition with water and nutrients, and enable the growth of a strong, vigorous tree. Weed management appeared to be the most important challenge in organic nurseries.

- **No synthetic pesticides.** Therefore, pest and disease susceptibility plays a bigger role, with multiple pests and diseases to deal with at the same time, and limited solutions to manage these. This causes also problems with the sanitary status of the plant propagation material.

Furthermore, organic breeding and testing focus on **additional traits**:

- No MCP ('Smartfresh') for storage allowed in organic (apple). Therefore, **storability** and post harvest disease tolerance plays a more important role.

- **Robustness and adaptability to climate change factors.** The traits related to climate change (drought stress sensitivity, resilience towards spring frost, sunburn, chilling requirement, earlier flowering period and harvest maturity), and change from region to region, are very difficult to assess, and also dependent on the rootstock, which makes it very difficult to tackle the adaptability to climate change through breeding.

- **New pests and diseases.** When testing for resistance/tolerance and as example succeeding for one fungal disease, sometimes another new or emergent fungal disease just takes over being the more "important one".

Some more general areas of needs in breeding and testing included:

- **Harmonization of data collection** and facilitating data exchange and access to information

- Lack of **markers** or practical **screening methods** for important pests and diseases, as well as abiotic factors.

- Higher **costs**, lack of funding, staff, and space.

Among innovative solutions in breeding and variety testing were mentioned:

- **Digitalization** of assessments to improve data quality and replicability, and save time.

- **Participative approaches**: participative breeding, on-farm testing to reduce costs, and testing the cultivars on multiple sites.

- Use of **original material** as parent with larger genetic base (old cultivars, landraces,...)

- Strengthen **networks** and create exchange **platforms** to improve collaboration and knowledge transfer.

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Introduction

The deliverables D 1.2 and D 1.3 are presented together, they were merged as their content is based on the results of a large survey, which was initially foreseen in the proposal to only assess the needs and lack of knowledge in organic breeding (D 1.3). Due to the fact that people contacted by the survey are mainly the same stakeholders for the two objectives, we commonly decided during the carry-out of the project to enlarge the questionnaire in order to assess and collect data on how is the current situation on organic fruit breeding methods, tools, genetic resources, and social/non-technological innovation (D 1.3).

What is organic breeding?

In organic breeding, aims and objectives are defined from the beginning to be in line with the specific needs of low-input organic farming systems. Each breeding step of screening and selecting elites and final varieties are done under organic growing conditions: no synthetical pesticides, no herbicides, and no mineral fertilizers. Therefore, organic breeding focuses on different traits (higher robustness, disease, and pest tolerance, resource/input-use higher efficiency) compared to conventional breeding, and uses different breeding approaches (breeding for enlarging the genetic diversity of base of varieties, promoting the use of well locally evaluated old cultivars as parents), and with different processes or tools (no genetic engineering). Organic breeding also often involves an ethical aspect, breeding is seen as a holistic approach and includes a participatory approach. Furthermore, varieties issued from organic breeding are often marketed differently, also more often targeting direct selling and/or on a more regional territory. Currently, most of the commercial fruit varieties used by organic growers have still been selected through conventional methods and in the best case, have been tested at the end of the selection process in organic experimental orchards.

We can also differentiate between Organic Plant Breeding (OPB) and Breeding for Organic (BfO). In Organic Plant Breeding (OPB), the focus is on the breeding process (see IFOAM definition in the box below): All breeding steps from crossing till final selections take place under organic conditions and the applied breeding techniques are in accordance with the techniques listed in the Annex of the position paper of IFOAM International for organic breeding from November 2017. In Breeding for Organic (BfO), the focus is on the product and the breeding goals which are specific to organic agriculture (e.g. disease tolerance), while not using critical breeding techniques and having the selection at least partially under organic conditions.

Definition of Organic Plant Breeding (OPB) by the [IFOAM International norms of 2014](#)

Article 4.8 Breeding of organic varieties

General Principles

Organic plant breeding and variety development is sustainable, enhances genetic diversity and relies on natural reproductive ability. It aims for new varieties particularly suited for organic production systems. Organic breeding is always creative, cooperative and open to science, intuition, and new findings. Organic plant breeding is a holistic approach that respects natural crossing barriers. Organic plant breeding is based on fertile plants that can establish a viable relationship with the living soil. Organic varieties are obtained by an organic plant breeding program.

Requirements:

4.8.1 To produce organic varieties, plant breeders shall select their varieties under organic conditions that comply with the requirements of this standard. All multiplication practices except meristem culture shall be under certified organic management.

4.8.2 Organic plant breeders shall develop organic varieties only based on genetic material that has not been contaminated by products of genetic engineering.

4.8.3 Organic plant breeders shall disclose the applied breeding techniques. Organic plant breeders shall make the information about the methods, which were used to develop an organic variety, available to the public latest from the beginning of the marketing of the seeds.

4.8.4 The genome is respected as an impartible entity. Technical interventions into the genome of plants are not allowed (e.g. ionizing radiation; transfer of isolated DNA, RNA, or proteins).

4.8.5 The cell is respected as an impartible entity. Technical interventions into an isolated cell on an artificial medium are not allowed (e.g. genetic engineering techniques; destruction of cell walls and disintegration of cell nuclei through cytoplasm fusion).

Organic breeding is facing more constraints

- (i) No mineral fertilizers, no herbicides → slower growth of the trees, the process takes longer, longer juvenile phase
- (ii) No synthetic pesticides → Pest and disease susceptibility plays a bigger role, with multiple pests and diseases to deal with at the same time
- (iii) New pests and diseases → When testing resistance and succeeding for one fungal disease, sometimes another fungal disease just takes over being the more “important one”
- (iv) No MCP for storage allowed (apple) → storability plays a bigger role

For many decades, nearly all fruit tree breeders were working for conventional and IPM most common growing systems and therefore, organic fruit growers had very few possibilities of choice for well-adapted varieties fitting with organic specific needs. On the other hand, skilled and experienced organic breeders were extremely sparse. Overall, combining general higher robustness (general adaptive capacities to abiotic and biotic stresses), good adaptability, and higher resource-

use efficiency with good market traits is particularly difficult in organic breeding, and there is more work and more years needed to select new varieties.

Survey to assess needs

To get a sharper understanding of the current fruit tree organic breeding needs and lack of knowledge across Europe a survey was carried out in the framework of the ‘InnOBreed’ project. The survey aimed to get a better identification of the needs in fruit breeding (from breeding to variety testing and finally, to fruit tree propagation schemes in the nursery) of pip fruits, stone fruits, almonds, grapes, and citrus. Up to now, it is the first survey organized at the European level which is focused on organic fruit tree breeding topic.

The questionnaire was designed to collect:

- Currently used methods, materials, and tools of breeding/testing
- Major traits focused on today and traits that may become more important in the future
- Areas of needs (and major cost factors for nurseries) and unresolved problems
- Innovative solutions - technical and social ones.

In parallel and with the same aim, questionnaires were also deeper developed on breeding steps/methods and more over on technical and social innovations which are on going at the level of case studies partners of the project.

Methods

Three different questionnaires were designed in cooperation with Danilo Christen (WBF) and Jean-Marc Audergon (INRAE) per targeted stakeholder group: breeders, variety testers, and nurserymen. The questionnaires included multiple choice questions to collect quantitative data, and open questions to collect qualitative data and go more in-depth.

The survey was completed by 126 respondents from 11 different countries. Figure 1 shows the exact overview by country and work of the respondents. In total, 44 breeders, 59 variety testers, and 23 nursery(wo)men answered the survey.

Figure 1: Breakdown of survey participants by country and work (Breeder, Variety tester, Nursery(wo)men).

In a second step, the output of the survey was reviewed during a workshop on 27.02.23 at FiBL in Frick with the project partners and some key stakeholders from different countries. Based on the survey results, the needs and problems were weighted and the most important topics were discussed.

In a third step, questionnaires filled in by case study partners were analysed and added value information was taken into account.

Breeders: breeding methods

Crops represented

A total of 44 answers from breeders were collected for all fruit species. Most breeders answering the survey are working with apples, followed by peach, apricot, pear, and cherry, other fruit crops were only represented by one or two breeders (Figure 2). Only a quarter of the breeders are developing breeding activities under organic rules.

Crop type	Crop	Count
Pip fruit	Apple (table)	19
Stone fruit	Peach (table)	9
Stone fruit	Apricot (table)	9
Pip fruit	Pear (table)	6
Stone fruit	Cherry (table)	5
Other	Citrus	2
Other	Almond	2
Stone fruit	Peach (for processing)	1
Stone fruit	Japanese plum	1
Other	Grape	1
Stone fruit	European plum (table)	1
Stone fruit	Cherry (for processing)	1

Figure 2: Number of completed questionnaires of breeders by fruit species.

Breeding criteria

For apples and pears, the breeding criteria ranked as most important were on one hand focused on fruit quality - e.g. taste (aroma) and firmness, to less extent, fruit firmness after storage, and appearance and on other hand, on the regularity of yield, disease (pest) tolerance/resistance (Figure 3). Most breeders have as objective to create new dessert varieties and a limited part of them have also as objective to work for processing objectives. Similarly, for apricot, cherry, and peach, the most important breeding criteria were fruit taste, firmness, regularity of yield, disease susceptibility (resp. harvesting period for cherry), appearance, and, additionally, self-fertility (Figure 4). Complementary information from case study questionnaires point out other important traits linked to complex notion of “robustness” – better adaptation capacity to overall abiotic and abiotic stresses, but also on fruit bearing habit/tree architecture and better plant adaptation to low input organic farming systems (e.g. higher nitrogen efficiency, better drought tolerance,...).

Figure 3: Rating of the importance of the breeding criteria requested by the respondents for pip fruit (1= not important at all; 5= very important).

Figure 4: Rating of the importance of the breeding criteria requested by the respondents for stone fruit.

Type of tools such as markers used in breeding

Mostly, depending on the fruit species, SNP and/or SSR markers are used. SCAR, PGS, and KASPAR are also used in some cases (Table 1).

Table 1: Diseases and pests for which markers are used.

Fruit species	Disease/ pest	Genes	Type of marker used
Apple	Apple scab (<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>)	Rvi6, Rvi2, Rvi4	SNP (6), SSR (2), SCAR (3)
	Powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>)		
	Rosy apple aphid (<i>Dysaphis plantaginea</i>)		SNP (2), SSR (1)
	Fireblight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>)		
	Storability		SNP
	Taste		SNP
	Harvest date		SNP
	Columnar growth	MdCo31 gene	
Pear	Fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>)		SSR (2)
Apricot	Self-incompatibility		
	Sharka/Plum Pox Virus resistance		PGS1.21 and ParPMC2 by PCR (2), SSR (1)
Cherry	Self-incompatibility	MGST gene mutation; S4' allele	
	Harvesting/maturity day		SNP (chr4_16353619)
	Flesh colour	PavMyb10.1	SNP (chr3_2393947)
	Firmness		SNP (chr4_16000421)
	Size and weight	PavCNR12	SNP (chr2_29787028)
Peach	Bacterial spot (<i>Xanthomonas arboricola</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>)		SNP
	Powdery mildew (<i>Sphaerotheca pannosa</i>)		SSR, SNP
	Leaf curl (<i>Taphrina deformans</i>)		SSR
	Green peach aphid (<i>Myzus persicae</i>)		SSR, KASPAR
Japanese plum	Self-incompatibility	consensus primers PaConsIF- PaConsIR2	

Diseases for which early screening methods in controlled conditions are used

In apples, screening methods are mainly used for the diseases apple scab (*Venturia inaequalis*) and to a lower extent, powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha*), but also for neonectria canker/European canker (*Neonectria ditissima*) (Table 2); one case study partner is developing early screening test to Rosy Aphid resistance (*Dysaphis plantaginea*). For peach, monilia twig blight and brown rot (*Monilia* spp.) and peach leaf curl (*Taphrina deformans*) were mentioned several times. For monilia twig blight (*Monilia laxa*) and bacterial canker (*Pseudomonas syringae*), a screening method is also used by at least one breeder for apricots and cherries. Three apricot breeders also reported using early stage screening methods for sharka/plum pox virus. For pears, only one person answered that they do screenings of fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*). The same applies to the screening methods for Marssonina apple blotch (*Diplocarpon coronariae*).

Table 2: Diseases by fruit species for which breeders are using screening methods.

fruit species	Name of the disease	Number of counts
Apple	Apple scab (<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>)	19
	Powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>)	12
	Neonectria canker/European canker (<i>Neonectria ditissima</i>)	8
	Marssonina apple blotch (<i>Diplocarpon coronariae</i>)	1
Pear	Fireblight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>)	1
Apricot	Sharka / Plum pox virus (PPV)	3
	Monilia twig blight (<i>Monilia laxa</i>)	2
	Bacterial canker (<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i>)	2
Peach	Monilia twig blight and brown rot (<i>Monilia</i> spp.)	5
	Peach leaf curl (<i>Taphrina deformans</i>)	4
Cherry	Monilia twig blight (<i>Monilia laxa</i>)	1
	Bacterial canker (<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i>)	1

Breeders: needs and innovative solutions

Steps of breeding and areas of needs

After having defined the main objectives, choosing adapted parents and crosses, the further breeding process of a new variety has been divided into five main steps (Figure 5). These five steps were weighted by the respondents according to their area of needs and importance. The step of pre-breeding – and/or having access to more robust parents - and the step of testing candidate lines were rated as the most important (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Five steps of breeding a new variety in chronological order.

Figure 6: Ranking of the five breeding steps/needs by importance. 1 = most important; 5 = least important.

Based on the five breeding steps, various open sub-questions were asked within the survey. The answers are summarised below supplemented with the outcome of the workshop at FiBL.

Pre-breeding more robust material

Within either getting access to right parents and/or pre-breeding material which express more robustness, some specific problem areas are expressed in a complementary way:

- (i) Maintaining genetic resources (work collections);
- (ii) Facilitate the exchange of genetic material (pollen/twigs), cf. sanitary status, policy, agreements (29 % but 48% say that there is no problem in having access to material);
- (iii) Facilitate the exchange of pre-breeding material
- (iv) Share data on genetic resources, access to valuable information/data on traits of potential parents

- (v) Integrating traits fitting with low input organic production (e.g. no copper use, very low nitrogen fertilizing, no/very low weeding control...)
- (vi) Integrating traits fitting with climate change

Maintaining genetic resources (Table 3) is expensive and seems not directly profitable. Public funding would be a possible solution to help maintain genetic resources, but in many cases, there is a lack of national and international funds, facilities, and staff. To reduce costs low-input and non-sprayed orchards and/or field collections would be a solution. Also, with the participatory approach, the genetic resources could be maintained on-farm as duplicates within a coordinated network of orchards spread in different parts of a country.

Another big problem that could represent a bottleneck for safe conservation and sharing original genetic resources is the sanitary status of the plant material regarding risk of diseases (e.g. Sharka/Plum Pox Virus, Peach Mosaic Virus, phytoplasma,...) as well as pests (e.g. aphids) and especially quarantine and Regulated Non Quarantine Pest (RNQP) pest & diseases. To avoid introducing new diseases there must be a higher control of plant material and/or a possibility for sanitary recovery/disease removal in case of infection of base plant material (government support, collaboration with companies). Useful would be also to work on more flexible EU Directives/Reglements that integrate exceptional lower sanitary rules specifically dedicated to facilitate movement of useful rare genetic resources used for scientific research and breeding purposes. Another worry are the new next-generation sequencing techniques which are constantly discovering new viruses or phytoplasma yet not known that negatively affect the import of plant material not only today but also retroactively. As an alternative to in-field maintenance of genetic resources, cryopreservation of cultivars and genotypes and centralized germplasm collection facilities with adequate infrastructure could help maintain original genetic resources and at least Virus Free material (Initial Material).

Access to genetic material. Most of the breeders have their own work collection as Figure 7 shows. The others get their genetic material from research institutes, other breeders, gene banks, and a few also from farmers/gardeners.

Figure 7: Number of breeders by the origin of their genetic material.

Two problems, in particular, have emerged from the **exchange of genetic material** (Table 4). On one hand, one third of the respondents expressed the difficulty access to public collections or the lack of sufficient public collections, and on the other hand some owners who do not allow to share their genetic material before it has been released. Public, centralized collections can be built or own gene banks can be created. Also, a good network of breeders and fruit tree genetic resource-holders (variety collectors and researchers) will help to facilitate the exchange of genetic material. In face of the common commercial competition between breeders, it's difficult to convince them to share their genetic material even in an earlier step. A non-commercial and collaborative approach on pre-breeding material would promote the possibility that every accession is available for everybody in the world for breeding purposes as it is already the case for genetic resources. Other possible solutions would be to find closely related plant material or to increase the accessibility to national germplasm at the European level. Also, agreements and exchanges would help to get improved and well evaluated genetic material. For example, with a more participative approach between breeders, such as: sharing half of the seeds from a crossing or sharing valuable pre-breeding material and sharing as consequence, success and benefit.

Not always (32%) there is available **valuable information** (Table 5) on potential parents tested under organic (low input) conditions available. In addition, one respondent expressed the problem of high access costs to scientific publications. Possible solutions would be to reduce the costs of accessing scientific publications or even make them available for free (Open source channels). Also, access to the latest scientific findings itself is a problem sometimes. Therefore, it's important to have a good network with other genebank curators, breeders, owners, and scientific institutes, to visit fruit expositions and field trips, and have good access to literature (internet, publications, results of projects, etc.).

For a exchange possibilities, there is a need to create platforms for discussion, exchange of experiences and regular meetings. However, there are already many such networks, the aim here should be to see who is not yet in a network and what exactly the needs are. If there are already networks that match the goals of InnOBreed, they should be supported and disseminated. Nevertheless, it is easier to achieve something by developing within a smaller group in a climate of confidence, here within the project and afterward spreading in the network. The survey also revealed a desire for a kind of chat room especially dedicated to organic breeders with a host for a quick exchange (e.g. share results of small trials or share ideas and ask for feedback).

To share and compare data with other breeders there is also a need for harmonization of the data collection (e.g. classification for growth trunks or ripening period). The best way to share the data would be a confirmed, centralized, and validated database. However, this means that not all data (e.g. traits) are always disclosed because of financial competition.

The survey showed that **integrating traits fitting with climate change** is also an important issue for breeders. To integrate traits there is again a big need for more economic resources, staff, and dedicated testing networks. Problematic is the speed and unpredictable climate changes compared to the lengthy breeding processes and also the fluctuation between the years. Moreover, the importance of the climatic event is depending on the fruit and region. While heat waves and drought have been given a very important weighting in both pip and stone fruits, new pests have been given more weight in pip

fruits than in stone fruits (Figure 8). On the other hand, the chilling requirement is a topic that is almost only relevant in stone fruit.

Due to the large climatic differences between the North and South of Europe, there should be at least two dedicated testing networks that focus on the problems of the respective region, but are still connected. In addition, regions should be defined in which the climatic conditions will develop in a similar direction.

Figure 8: Ranking of the most relevant climatic events for pip fruits (left) and stone fruits (right).

The most relevant climatic event, heat wave (sharp increase in sunlight/temperature over a short period), causes sunburn on fruits or leaves, induces changes in fruit texture, and decreases storability. Drought (long period of lack of precipitation) negatively affects flower bud induction and fruit set in the following year, leading to lower yield and/or negative effects on fruit quality like an increase in the number of double fruits the following year or smaller fruit size. In pip fruit there were new pests listed like *Halyomorpha halys* - Stink bug, Apple blossom weevil, *Cydia pomonella* - Codling moth and new diseases like Blossom wilt (*Sclerotinia* sp.), *Elsinoë piri*, Marssonina (*Diplocarpon coronariae*) and finally, new scab races. In stone fruit, on the other hand, there was only one new disease: *Taphrina deformans* (Apricot), and a few new pests like *Drosophila suzukii* (Apricot and Cherry), *Halyomorpha halys* - Stink bug (Apricot), *Pseudococcus* (Apricot) listed in the survey.

Due to the climatic change the flowering time is earlier everywhere in Europe, but the date for the last spring frost event has not been advancing to the same degree, so the period with spring frost risks is becoming longer/wider. During the workshop, it became clear that especially the flower frost tolerance has to be improved. This could require simulations, for example in a climate chamber, and more knowledge about possible levels on this traits. Last decades, also hail events in spring/summer increased significantly. Through anticipating more and more, the blooming time and therefore fruit disorders like split-pit, skin discoloration, and double fruit are more frequent in stone fruits. Chilling requirements might become a problem shortly for stone fruit and especially in Southern Europe. Also, new postharvest disorders and prolonged summer rainfalls became more and more important.

The workshop highlighted that the nutritional quality of the fruit also has a decisive value in society. For example, people want to become healthier by eating an apple with a lot of secondary metabolites like polyphenols, plant fibers and/or vitamins, which e.g. the variety 'Gala' does not offer. In general,

the workshop emphasized the need to change the priorities of important traits that are used for selection to address future issues. The work of creating a cultivar ideotype within InnOBreed will help to address this issue.

Table 3: Maintaining genetic resources (work collections).

Problem	Possible putative solution
Expensive and not profitable/viable	Public funding to maintain fruit tree collections at research institutes
Lack of national and international funds, facilities, and personnel - 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participatory approach, safe duplication in a coordinated network of high-stem orchard meadows spread in different parts of the country - Low input orchards to reduce the costs - In-field collection
Sanitary status of the plant material: diseases (e.g. Sharka infection and PNRSv (peach mosaic), Apple Proliferation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration between Public Institutes and with Private companies for virus/phytoplasma disease removal of basic plant material - Higher control for plant materials to avoid introducing new diseases - Government support for sanitation (like from viruses etc.) - More flexible EU/US laws (exception rules for genetic resources used in breeding and research; new NGS techniques are discovering e.g. new viruses yet not known - that negatively affect the import of plant material not only today but also retroactively) - Cryopreservation of cultivars and genotypes (e.g. Virus Free material) - Centralized germplasm collection facilities with adequate infrastructure
Sanitary status of the plant material: pests (e.g. aphids)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cryopreservation of cultivars and genotypes (e.g. Virus Free material) - 2 - Centralized or virtual coordinated germplasm collection facilities with adequate infrastructure (AEGIS)

Table 4: Facilitate the exchange of genetic material (pollen/twigs), cf. sanitary status, policy, and agreements.

Problem	Possible solution
Difficult access to or no public collections (29%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build public centralized germplasm collections - Own gene bank or collection of old cultivars - 9 - Network of breeders and Fruit Tree Genetic Resources holders (variety collectors & researchers) - 9
The owner does not allow to share their pre-breeding genetic material → In the face of the commercial success of breeders this isn't easy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use the third person to avoid struggles. A law that every accession is available for everybody in the world for breeding purposes (not commerce) - 1 - Try to find closely related plant material - 2 - Increase the accessibility to non-protected national germplasm at a worldwide level - Waiting till the breeding number is registered and starting crosses with it than - Agreements and exchange - more participative approach between breeders (e.g. share half the seeds from a crossing, or share pre-breeding material and share the success) - Provision of pollen from pre-breeding material with innovative traits (multiple resistances, original traits) to breeders

Table 5: Share data on genetic resources, and access to valuable information/data on traits of potential parents.

Problem	Possible solution
Data collection not harmonized	Harmonization needed for data collection (e.g. classification for growth trunks or ripening period) - 1
No common database	Confirmed, centralized, and validated database - 4
Cost of accessing data	Reduce the costs of accessing scientific publications or even make them available for free - 1
Competition: sometimes need to hide something (traits etc.)	Own database - 6
Lack of information on potential parents (especially tested under organic/low input) – 32% expressed the problem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve EURISCO – ECPGR Central Crop Database – in sharing harmonized evaluation data from FTGR collections - More core collections with sharing evaluation data
Difficulty to access (up-to-date) information/ research results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Having a network for sharing information (other breeders, owners, colleagues, Institutes) - 12 – Visit fruit expositions, field trips, Internet, Literature, publications, and results of projects - 3 – Chat room for breeders with a host (e.g. share results of small trials or share ideas and ask for feedback) – Workshop.

Table 6: Integrating traits fitting with climate change.

Problem	Possible solution
Timeline of climatic change (very quick, fluctuating) vs. a timeline of breeding programs	Modeling of future conditions Selection of “broad” vs. “narrow” adaptation
Different climate change impacts and needs in different regions. E.g. Hardiness of dormant buds for northern-limit zones or low-chill requirements for regions with warmer climates is further examples of resilience.	Need for a dedicated testing network. At least 2 testing networks depending on different climatic regions. Early involvement of growers from different climatic conditions.
Some traits are related to each other. E.g. The dynamic interaction between chilling and heat requirements makes it challenging to create cultivars with a low late frost susceptibility/high heat requirement (to program the bloom time) and a modest chilling requirement (guaranteed to be satisfied).	Breeding varieties for local climate adaptation. E.g. chilling requirements are very important, especially in the south, less so in the north depending on region, while late frost is especially in the north → different breeding programs needed
Some traits related to climate change are very difficult to assess, e.g. late frost susceptibility	Simulate frost e.g. in a climate chamber → More economic resources and staff are needed
The rootstock also plays a role in climate change adaptability, e.g. drought tolerance	Rootstock trials and variety x rootstock interaction trials.

Selection of candidate lines

During the selection of candidate lines, pragmatic and efficient **screening** methods is a major challenge (36,4 %). Three categories can be made for which the screening methods can be applied.

These are screening methods for **polygenic disease tolerance, pest tolerance and drought tolerance, or other traits fitting with climate change**. The biggest problem with screening methods is that some are missing and others are too complicated and time-consuming (Table 7). If a screening method is missing, a well-developed network with other breeders across Europe helps to exchange information with each other and with scientists to exchange information that has not yet been published. Within such a network, new methods could also be (further) developed and tested. Another possibility would be a database with information on traits. This issue is linked with the access to valuable information/data, look there for further information. Also, a platform on which all diseases and pests are listed and for each of them a sheet of information about the screening methods would be very useful. It should be very simple and practical and there should be one or two times a year an online discussion to adapt it.

Not many people can apply specific screening methods, so it's important that the method is easy, efficient and so far, many people can apply the method. The time needed to obtain detailed information on breeding material is sometimes very long. For the simplification and shortening of complex and time-consuming methods, cheap multi-traits analysis screening methods (e.g. molecular markers) would be beneficial. Visual and digital picture analysis methods and artificial inoculation could also contribute greatly to the simplification of methods. To improve the precision of a method, one approach would be to do the screening in the field, so that the environment is as similar as possible to the conditions in which the plants will grow later for fruit production. If this does not work, it is important to pay attention to the composition of the soil: is it fertilized, low, or not?

Finally, the climate also plays a decisive role here. Due to the climatic conditions at a precise phenological stage, in some cases, the evaluation can not be performed. A possible solution would be to extend the period of observation and/or to enlarge the number of selection sites, but this would again require more staff and money. An exact simulation of climatic events is not possible; therefore, breeders should be trained to know exactly how to act when a specific climatic event occurs. During the workshop on pip fruit, it was decided to focus on flower frost tolerance, fruit and leaves sunburn, lack of fruit coloration, leaf health tolerance, and apple glassiness (watercore). Also, the priorities of important traits that are used for selection may need to be changed. Also, traits need to be compared with plasticity and traits with stability. Furthermore, an important approach is not only to select resistant varieties but also tolerant ones.

Through the workshop, it was seen that the screening methods and their problems can differ between pip and stone fruit. Therefore, the question arose whether there should be networks not only based on climatic regions but also on the fruit type.

Table 7: Problems and possible solutions of screening methods.

Problem	Possible solution
Access to information about screening methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Making methods public, already at an early stage – Publish established screening methods
<p>Methods missing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Biotic stress: pests, diseases (e.g. Pseudomonas on cherry) – Abiotic stress e.g. chilling requirement, frost tolerance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Define methods and see who might already be using them, develop, test, and establish screening methods within an expert group (e.g. EUFRIN network) – Network with other breeders across Europe: develop common approaches if there are similar challenges, exchange if there are existing screening methods elsewhere – Platform on which all diseases and pests are listed and for each problem, there is an A4 sheet on which the screening methods are explained, very simple and very practical. online discussion 1-2 times a year – Chat room where you can quickly exchange information if you have problems → needs someone to manage it – More exchange/ support from/collaboration with research for specific questions (e.g. Marssonina screening) that are not yet published – Own method with a genetic marker – More research needed on these traits (ecophysiology, ...)
<p>Methods too difficult</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Biotic stress: pest tolerance, disease tolerance (Fire blight, Scab, European canker, vascular diseases, storage diseases) – Abiotic higher nitrogen efficiency <p>→ not precise enough → time-consuming → technically difficult → traits with plasticity vs. stability.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Seedlings in the field with no spraying condition for 3 years – “survival of the fittest” – Visual and digital picture analysis methods – More rapid and cheap multi-analysis screening methods (e.g. molecular markers) – Artificial inoculation (e.g. for scab, mildew, alternaria leaf blotch) – Phenotypic screening in the field. The closer the selection environment to the environment in which the plants are supposed to be grown, the more precise the screening (Genotype x Environment x Management effects)
Lack of staff	More skilled team or supported /paid internship
Climatic events cannot be simulated, but it would be good for the breeders to know what to look out for when such an event takes place	<p>List of Climatic events and then what to look out for</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Frost injuries on flowers ii. Sunburn on fruits & leaves iii. Lack of fruit coloration (too hot autumns) iv. Leaf heat tolerance v. Watercore on apple
Due to the climatic conditions at a precise phenological stage, in some cases, the evaluation can not be performed	Extend the period of observation (number of years) and/or enlarge the number of selection sites
Problems of too low correlation between controlled conditions screening methods and/or markers on young plantlets and in open field conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Screening methods need to be validated -Selection could be based on ‘tolerance’ or ‘quantitative resistance’ and not only on monogenic resistant genes

Testing candidate lines

On one hand, most of the respondents (40,9 %) expressed that there was no major challenge in testing candidate lines under organic production rules in other hand, three main themes emerged from the survey. Having a **network of sites for testing in different environments** is one of them. The other ones are **testing the candidate lines under organic conditions and low input conditions** (22,7 %) (Table 8). The main issue here is a lack of economic resources, time, organic-testing fields, and staff. A possible approach to solve this would be a participatory approach with private gardens, farmers, contractual partners, and research centers. To this also the farmers needed to be trained on what to do and when to do it. Also, too high pressure of pests and fungal diseases is a problem because it causes big losses and it impedes the assessment of other parameters.

Table 8: Testing the candidate lines under organic conditions.

Problem	Possible solution
Lack of economic resources	Participate approach: Organic fruit growers, Private gardens, on-farm – low input organic or in non-sprayed conditions.
Lack of time, organic test fields, and staff	Contractual partners, research centers - 12
Too high pressure of pests (e.g. <i>Agrilus sinuatus</i> (Sinuate Pear-tree Borer) (Pear), ESFY, voles) and fungal diseases (collective disease pressure more harmful than only one) that cause many losses and make assessments of other parameters difficult, especially under no/low PP	Minimal plant protection needed → No-Spray conditions for the first selection stages (<u>Except single, possible treatments against relevant insect pests</u>) until positive selections become grafted on standard rootstocks (M9/M25...), then a low-input or organic standard treatment

Marketing

22,7% of the respondents say to had significant challenges in marketing new varieties and reasons are the fact that (1) it is not easy to find the right partners especially for Formal sector Institutes for which marketing is far from their core activities, (2) it need more investment (budget & skilled people). Some solutions have been proposed:

- (i) Increase consumer acceptance of new varieties (e.g. education of consumers)
- (ii) Participatory approach: Involvement of the supply chain operators
- (iii) Facilitate the introduction of new varieties in retailers
- (iv) Developing new marketing concepts
- (v) Implement marketer-trainings for sellers on traits and background of varieties
- (vi) Developing an umbrella trademark for fruit species that cannot be sold under the variety name

Registration

Only 16% of respondents have significant challenges with the registration of new varieties and therefore there is a limited need of improvements despite the following suggestions:

- (i) Reduce the price of registration

- (ii) Reduce administrative work
- (iii) Reduce the time between registration filings and final results
- (iv) Difficulties to predict how wide the protection is needed.

Most of breeders are following formal EU and or National registration channels (CPVO/OCVV, INOV,...) and in limited cases, varieties are released in ‘Open source’ conditions.

Using old cultivars as parents

Only ten percent of respondents are using ‘old varieties’ as parents in more than 50% of their total number of crosses. Thirty people stated that they had no problems with the use of old cultivars as parents. Twenty people have problems with **negative traits** and ten ones report that there is a **lack of information** on old cultivars. Other people reported problems with the **availability of healthy plant reproductive material and genetic material of old cultivars** (Free of quarantine pests & diseases) (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Problems of using old cultivars as parents.

The following were listed as examples of observed negative traits:

- (i) Fruit quality (loss of size, fruit flesh, hard skin, texture, appearance, bad taste, softness, weak colour, short peduncle) - 13
- (ii) Low storability - 6
- (iii) Higher chilling requirements - 3
- (iv) High susceptibility to pests and diseases – 3
- (v) High risk of fruit drops near harvest time (Apple) – 3
- (vi) Irregular yield (Apple) - 2
- (vii) Low sugar content (Apple, Peach) - 2
- (viii) Self-incompatibility (Almond, Peach) - 2

Old cultivars can express fruit qualities which were particularly expected in the past time but it depends on the diversity of cultivars, they are also part of good crosses. The information about old cultivars is sometime expressed to be too sparse and incomplete. For apples, only some traits are

known and/or communicated. Also, there is a lack of knowledge about resistance/susceptibility to diseases and pests and there is unreliable information for peach regarding PLC susceptibility. The availability of genetic material of old varieties is sometime problematic because these could suffer from phytosanitary issues, accumulated along the clonal propagation history (Peach). Also, almonds trees are usually affected by viruses and fungal diseases. Two cases have challenges along to get trees from public gene banks (Apple & Apricot). Further comments said that offspring split much more into the next generations (e.g. fruit size) (Apple) and that there is a low genetic variability for peaches.

Tracking technical and social already developed innovations

(i) Original breeding material used as parents

More resilient organic farming systems need to fully integrate larger genetic diversity importance – e.g. by more using old original varieties and landraces in breeding activities and therefore it was not surprisingly that most of respondents to the survey declare to use to some extent, old cultivars as parents (95%). It is rather not clear which definition of ‘old cultivar’ has been used, e.g. for apple, ‘Golden Delicious’ is historically “old” (1890) but has nothing to do with a real old robust local landrace.

Some key case studies have really (8) founded they organic breeding programme on using mainly local well evaluated old cultivars and landraces as donors of quantitative traits like pest & disease tolerance, more robustness, low input farming adaptability,...(mainly focused on apple).

(ii) Original breeding traits and breeding methods

Even if there is still an urgent need of adapted and efficient new screening methods and descriptors, some traits are more and more emphasized either by important consequences of climate change (Drought tolerance, sunburn, flower frost, chilling requirement,...) for which some new approaches have been partially implemented such as (1) looking for new parents – e.g. higher sunburn or foliage tolerance, russet fruit types; (2) looking for better combinations between varieties and somewhat stronger rootstocks; (3) enlarging the geographical network of screening/testing sites – e.g. participatory approaches).

On the other hand, more resilient organic farming systems need to fully integrate lower input dependances to plant protection products and organic fertilizers for which new traits and methods are partially on going implemented such as (1) ‘robustness’ and ‘vitality’ for which ad hoc definitions, components traits and descriptors need still to be commonly defined; (2) tolerance and/or quantitative disease resistance has been already tackled as concept and screening methods for some diseases have been published by some breeders, others are not published; (3) interestingly, survey revealed that at least eleven apple breeders are using Marker Assisted Selection (MAS) for scab, two for ‘Rosy Apple Aphid’ and one on pear is using it for Fire Blight. Concerning stone fruit species, four MAB tools are used for three important disease resistance genes (Peach), two others on apricot concerning Sharka resistance and one for aphid resistance on Peach; (4) at least six case studies (Apple, pear, peach, apricot) are already developing long term experimental evaluation orchards and elite selection trial in non sprayed and/or very low fertilizing input and/or in agroforestry projects and or in high stem standard trees orchard meadows in order to screen most robust, disease tolerant and higher nitrogen efficiency traits.

Concerning improving fruit quality, high throughput evaluation methods (mostly infrared spectroscopy) are already tested by at least five partners, on cherry, MAS is used for four fruit quality traits and on apple, it is also used for one fruit quality trait.

Original methods have are also mentioned by four case studies

(iii) Original social approaches

First of all, integration of large public and farmers for prospecting and safeguarding old endangered old local varieties and landraces where the best performing ones are used as parent is one of the key element for several organic breeders (7). Such link is also used for testing variety preference by large public during ‘Old local cultivars’ events or exhibitions.

From the survey, 41% of the respondents say that they had already the plan in implementing participatory approaches at one or other step of the selection.

Some key case studies (6) are already implementing at one level or another the concept of “Participatory breeding” by integrating old varieties collection or fruit genebank managers, breeders, fruit growers, nurseries and consumers. One case has created an original concept of breeding – open- pollinated historical national varieties - with the close integration of a network of amateur gardeners. Other interesting social innovations are pointed out like specific the co-creation of rules and formal agreements which are necessary tools which help to build mutual confidence, fair benefit sharing and the development of local or short trade circuits.

At another level, innovative Public, Private, People Partnerships (PPPP) have been highlighted where agreements have been defined between old varieties collection or fruit genebank managers, nursery stock managers, nurseries (SME’s) and large public for releasing best performing old local or landraces fuit varieties.

There is also a need of other social innovation such as a kind of “chat room” for sharing questions, results and experiences between European organic breeders.

Variety testers: testing methods

Crops represented

A total of 59 answers from variety testers were collected for all fruit species. Most testers answered the survey testing apple (table), followed by pear (table), cherry (table), European plum (table), and peach (table). All other fruit crops were mentioned significantly less (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Number of responses from variety testers by fruit species.

Traits assessed

For both stone and pome fruit, the characteristics of aroma and appearance were assessed by almost all participants (Figure 11). Over 30 of the respondents stated that they evaluate disease susceptibility in apples. Most of the respondents also rated apricots and peaches as disease susceptible. With pears, on the other hand, more value is placed on the harvesting period and regularity of yield. These two characteristics are also in the top five for apples, apricots, and peaches. In the case of cherries, the assessment of firmness/texture is also very important.

Figure 11: Traits assessment of apple, pear, apricot, cherry, and peach.

Pests and diseases assessed

The variety testers were asked which pests and diseases they evaluate. In apples, the variety testers are mainly testing level of susceptibility to apple scab (*Venturia inaequalis*), powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha*), Nectria canker/European canker (*Neonectria ditissima*), Fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*) and to Storage diseases. For each fruit listed here, Monilia Rot plays a role in variety testing. For Pears, pear scab (*Venturia pyrina*) on leaves, fruit and twigs, Fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*), and *Stemphylium* leaf blight (*Stemphylium vesicarium*) were mentioned as diseases that variety testers check for. For apricots and peaches, the diseases Plum rust (*Tranzchelia* spp.), and Powdery mildew (*Podosphaera tridactyla*) are looked at. In addition, a few testers are looking at Bacterial canker (*Pseudomonas syringae*) in apricots and Peach leaf curl (*Taphrina deformans*) in peaches.

Aphids play an important role in variety testing for each fruit listed here. While in pome fruit many variety testers pay attention to codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*), in apricot and peach they mainly look for leafhoppers and earwigs. Some pests affect apples and peaches, for example, the brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha halys*) and the leafrollers/tortrix moths. Especially by apples, the tester assesses the apple sawfly (*Hoplocampa testudinea*) and the apple blossom weevil (*Anthonomus pomorum*), by pears the pear psylla (*Cacopsylla pyri*), and by cherries the spotted wing drosophila (*Drosophila suzukii*) and the cherry fruit fly (*Rhagoletis cerasi*).

Table 9: Main pest and disease susceptibility assessments by crops.

Crop	Disease/ Pest	Name of the disease/ pest	Number of counts
Apple	Diseases	Apple scab (<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>)	36
		Powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>)	30
		Nectria canker/European canker (<i>Neonectria ditissima</i>)	15
		Fireblight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>)	10
		Storage diseases	9
		Marsssonina apple blotch (<i>Diplocarpon coronariae</i>)	4
		Sooty blotch	4
		Anthraxnose (<i>Elsinoë piri</i>)	3
	Pests	Aphids (in total)	32
		- Rosy apple aphid (<i>Dysaphis plantaginea</i>)	12
		- Woolly apple aphid (<i>Eriosoma lanigerum</i>)	7
		Codling moth (<i>Cydia pomonella</i>)	11
		Apple sawfly (<i>Hoplocampa testudinea</i>)	5
		Brown marmorated stink bug (<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>)	4
		Apple blossom weevil (<i>Anthonomus pomorum</i>)	3
Mites		2	
Pear	Diseases	Leafrollers/tortrix moths	2
		Pear scab (<i>Venturia pyrina</i>)	2
		Fireblight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>)	2
		Stemphylium leaf blight (<i>Stemphylium vesicarium</i>)	2
	Pests	Monilia fruit rot (<i>Monilia</i> spp.)	1
		Pear psylla (<i>Cacopsylla pyri</i>)	2
		Aphids	2
		Lace bug (<i>Stephanitus pyri</i>)	1
Apricot	Diseases	Sinuate peartree borer (<i>Agrilus sinuatus</i>)	1
		Codling moth (<i>Cydia pomonella</i>)	1
		Monilia twig blight (<i>Monilia laxa</i>)	4
		Plum rust (<i>Tranzschelia</i> spp.)	3
		Bacterial canker (<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i>)	2
	Pests	Powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera tridactyla</i>)	2
		Sharka / Plum pox virus (PPV)	1
		Aphids	2
Peach	Diseases	Leafhoppers	2
		Earwigs	2
		Monilia twig blight (<i>Monilia laxa</i>)	2
		Monilia brown rot (<i>Monilia</i> spp.)	2
		Powdery mildew (<i>Sphaerotheca pannosa</i>)	2
		Peach leaf curl (<i>Taphrina deformans</i>)	2
	Pests	Bacterial leaf spot (<i>Xanthomonas</i> spp.)	1
		Plum rust (<i>Tranzschelia</i> spp.)	1
		Green peach aphid	1
		Brown marmorated stink bug (<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>)	1
Cherry	Diseases	Leafhoppers	1
		Leafrollers/tortrix moths	1
		Black cherry aphid (<i>Myzus cerasi</i>)	2
	Pests	Cherry leaf spot (<i>Blumeriella jaapi</i>)	1
		Cherry fruit fly (<i>Rhagoletis cerasi</i>)	2
		Spotted wing drosophila (<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>)	2

Testing environment

Most of the respondents test their varieties under standard conventional/IPM or standard organic conditions. Apples are also often planted in low-input conventional/IPM and almonds in low-input organic systems for testing. Very few of the respondents are testing in experimental agroforestry and/or orchard meadows and have no plant protection (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Production systems or regimes under which the varieties are tested.

Testing system

Around 2/3 of respondents test all or some of the varieties on-farm. Besides, 63% of respondents only test the varieties on one standard rootstock (M9), and only 37% study the interactions between varieties and rootstocks.

Used descriptors

The majority of variety testers use descriptors (Figure 13). The descriptors of the European Fruit Research Institutes Network (Eufirin) are used most frequently. Almost half as many mainly use the descriptors of the European Cooperative Programme for Plant Genetic Resources (ECPGR) and only a small proportion use their own, others, or the descriptors of the International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV).

*eufirin: European Fruit Research Institutes Network

*ECPGR: European Cooperative Programm for Plant Genetic Resources

Figure 13: Descriptors that are mostly used.

Variety testers: needs and innovative solutions

Field assessment/ data collection

One of the main problems is a **lack of funding and personnel for conducting testing over a long perio** (Table 10). Especially for a reliable dataset, it is important to collect data for more than three or four years. Besides more money, faster and simpler methods are needed to save time and personnel. An example of this would be image analysis, such as apps for crop monitoring, or the automation of post-harvest measurements. Improved use of **databases** also saves time, as direct data input in the field via tablet can save the need for paper. It should be noted, however, that comments are still written and backups made. At the same time, such digital methods could also address the problem of **harmonization of the data collection**. This is because technology always measures or assesses the same over the years and is not dependent on the subjective perception of one or more people. Periodical assessment and matching notations scales between different variety testers also contribute to the harmonization of the data. A few respondents also mentioned **replicability** in different locations and microclimates as a problem. This can easily be solved by on-farm trials at different locations. Also, local advisors can work with farmers to get feedback from them and so validate the data.

To test fruit quality/taste and maturity assessment, there is a need for **non-destructive tools** applicable to a large number of different varieties. Setting up a mini panel methodology for assessment of the fruit quality, as a complement of an expert note, would be a possible solution. Furthermore, two more detailed problems were described. It was shown that when assessing the susceptibility to **Monilia rot**, the time of flowering must also be considered to be able to weigh the monilia damage. This can be achieved by an accurate assessment of apricot flower phenology and weather conditions. Furthermore, using the example of *Drosophila suzukii*, it was shown that if fruit quality and pest susceptibility are assessed simultaneously in a trial, this can influence each other. In trials with fewer insecticides, damage by pests can impact the evaluation of varieties. A possible solution would be to carry out the variety trials under insect-proof structures for example close some branches with an anti-insect net and so preserve some fruits for the following evaluations. But the costs of this are high.

Table 10: Significant challenges with field assessments/ data collection in the last few years.

Problem	Possible solution
Harmonized data collection/repeatability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Higher investment in technology for field assessment will save time, and labor and could improve results regarding comparability between performing persons and years – Creation of notations scales to harmonize the notations between experimenters and centers (e.g. yield, susceptibility to diseases...) – Periodical assessment and not only when it occurs that it's important
Better use of database	Use of digital robust and efficient tablets to directly save the field data – Problem with making comments and no backup
Having enough funding available for conducting testing over a long period	More funding for a longer period (not only 3 years) → Collecting 3-4 years of data is sometimes not enough for a reliable dataset
Having enough personnel available for conducting testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Using image analysis for rapid and sound assessment – Automatization of some measurements - especially post-harvest ones – Digital solutions, such as apps for crop monitoring using a tablet or smartphone
Repeatability at different locations/microclimates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Evaluation on multiple sites with same harmonized methods & descriptors => need of capacity building – On-farm screening
On-farm screening: quality of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Adapt the evaluation criteria (simplify). No detailed assessments as at research stations but rather a limited number of information (e.g. productivity, growth habit, pruning...) – Develop a simple App or online survey, let the advisors do the assessments or get the feedback from farmers, getting oral feedback is much easier and “yields” more than on paper
Influence of low input on testing e.g. <i>Drosophila suzukii</i> : damage caused by decreased insecticides could impact the evaluation of varieties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Carry out the variety trials under insect-proof structures. But the cost of this is high. – Close some branches with an anti-insect net and so preserve some fruits for the following evaluations
Influence of weather conditions on diseases and pests e.g. consider the blooming period of apricot into monilia susceptibility on flowers	Accurate assessment of apricot flower phenology and weather conditions to weigh monilia damages
Fruit quality (taste): need for non-destructive tools for fruit quality and maturity assessment adapted to a great number of varieties/species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Setting up a mini panel methodology for assessment of fruit quality (as a complement of an expert note) – Testing at several locations and over several years ensures that enough fruit is produced
How to assess climate change-relevant traits? (drought stress sensitivity, resilience towards spring frost, sunburn, chilling requirement)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Modelling → 1st phenotype is needed → physiological reaction to climate impact (example: “Ref.- Population”)

Testing of varieties under organic production conditions

Again, there is a **lack of staff and space** (Table 11). The space problem could be solved through the participatory approach by planting directly in orchards from professional producers. As there is a shortage of qualified staff, farmers could collect the data directly from their orchards. However, this will most likely result in a drop in the quality of the data, as the methods are too time-consuming and complicated, and it is difficult to get the farmers to the trees at the right time for data collection. It would be possible to simplify the evaluation criteria or to develop a simple app or online survey. Also, oral feedback would be much easier for the farmers and yields more than on paper. Also, sometimes the **notation scales** of conventional do not fit to the organic production conditions. For this, the scales would have to be adapted for the organic sector. All other problems listed are caused by too **high pest and disease pressure**. For example, the problem of low/no phytosanitary protection can be solved by tolerant/resistant varieties. Due to the high pest and disease pressure, it is impossible to assess other traits, and also genotypes do not unfold their full potential. Extreme weather conditions can also play the same role. By comparing varieties in the same environment, the problem could be partially circumvented. In addition, the most susceptible varieties could already be sorted out by pre-selecting five to ten trees under low-input organic conditions. In addition, there is always the emergence of new pests and diseases. Visiting participatory selection orchards can help to identify new pests and diseases. For these, new criteria of testing have to be introduced.

Table 11: Significant challenges with testing of the varieties under organic production conditions in the last few years.

Problem	Possible solution
Evaluation under low/no phytosanitary protection: very high pest or disease pressure (e.g. leaf curling/peach)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Disease resistance – More funding to buy fertilizers
New pests or diseases appeared	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Introducing new criteria for testing – Visits to participatory selection orchards
Sometimes the scales of conventional do not fit organic production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – New/adapted notations scales – Test conventional
Site-specific problems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Weather – pressure of pests and diseases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – impossible to assess others' traits – Genotypes do not unfold their full potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Comparison with other varieties – Monitoring water needs and the evolution of soil nutrient levels – 1. test phase: 5 to 10 trees tested under low-input organic conditions – 2. testing (if it performs very well): 20 to 50 trees under standard organic production conditions
Lack of space and staff	On-farm testing, directly in orchards from professional producers (Participatory selection)

Novel traits, which become more important for organic production

Most of the respondents said that they think that **adaptation traits to climate change**, such as tolerance to extreme weather conditions, will become increasingly important for organic farming in the future (Table 12). Drought stress sensitivity, resilience to spring frost, cold requirements of fruit trees, and adaptation to sunburn were mentioned as examples. In the workshop, it was highlighted that phenotypic data are needed to be able to model the physiological response to climate change (example: "ref. population"). New traits for **disease and pest susceptibility** were listed second most frequently. The diseases scab, Marssonina coronariae (*Diplocarpon coronariae*), fire blight, fruit tree canker, anthracnose (*Elsinoë piri*), and the pest aphids and especially the woolly apple aphid were mentioned. Almost only a third of the respondents thought of novel traits for **long shelf life and tolerance to storage diseases**, such as fruit quality, taste, aesthetics of skin and colour, and consumer preference. A few times, more **consistent yields** across growing seasons, better **autonomy in nutrients and water** (e.g. carbon farming parameters), resistance to **abiotic/biotic stress**, and **cultivation technology** were also mentioned as possible important new traits for organic production in the future. In the case of cultivation technology, the life span of orchards, fertilization management, and irrigation management were mentioned as examples. In contrast, broader **adaptability to different environments, frugality, rootstock, pre-harvest drop sensitivity, and microbiome analysis** was listed only once or twice. **Non-destructive methods** related to tree architecture and fruit quality traits, as well as analytical trials on the susceptibility of varieties to **bio-aggressors with intra- and inter-site replications**, are also expected to play a more important role in the future. In addition to the traits, it was also noted that uniform methods for data collection and data evaluation are needed to be able to compare varieties across regions. Also, the number of recorded traits can only be expanded if breeding companies and licensees co-finance variety testing. Considering the many possible susceptibilities, it can be said that it is better to have good overall tolerance than total resistance to one trait.

Table 12: Novel traits which become more and more important for organic production in the future.

Trait	Examples	Number of counts
Climate change adaptation		
	Drought stress sensitivity	4
	Resilience toward spring frost	3
	Fruit tree chilling requirement	2
	Adapted to sunburn	1
Disease and pest susceptibility		
	Scab	2
	<i>Marssonina</i> and <i>Elsinoë</i> apple blotch/anthracnose	2
	Fire blight	1
	Aphids	1
	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>	1
	Fruit tree European canker	1
Woolly apple aphid	1	
Long storability and tolerance to storage/post harvest diseases		
	Fruit quality	6
	Taste	1
	Aesthetics of the skin and color	1
	Consumer preference	1
More consistent yield across growing seasons		5
Autonomy in nutrients and water (e.g. carbon farming parameters)		4
Resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses		3
Cultivation technology		
	Lifespan of the orchards	1
	Fertilization management	1
	Irrigation management	1
Broader adaptability to different environments	Larger geographical testing network	2
Frugality	Testing nitrogen efficiency	2
Rootstock		
	Important for water stress	1
	Higher vigour improves weed control	1
Pre-harvest drop sensitivity		1
Microbiome analysis		1
Non-destructive methods related to tree architecture and fruit quality traits.	Image analyses, LIDAR, NIRS technologies	1
Analytical trial on the susceptibility of varieties to bio-aggressors, with intra-site and multi-site repetitions		1

Nurseries: problems and needs

The nursery(wo)men were asked to state their difficulties and biggest cost factors to produce high-quality organic trees. The results showed that weed management (no herbicides) is the main difficulty and also the highest cost factor (Figure 14). This is mainly due to the high working costs of mechanical weed control. Furthermore, many struggles with plant protection (no synthetic pesticides allowed) and fertilization (no mineral fertilizers allowed). Another cost factor besides weed management is the grafting work/production of mother plants. Again, knowledge is an important tool to minimize difficulties and cost factors. This requires good literature, more research, and good dissemination of knowledge.

Figure 14: Main difficulties and cost factors to produce high-quality organic trees.

Weed management (minutes of the workshop)

The workshop showed that especially in the first two years, weed management is of great importance. **Mechanical weeding, biological herbicides, liquid mulch, or essential oils** can be used to control weeds. **Cover plants** could also be planted between the trees, or **chickens** could be kept on the plantation to eat the weeds. Another very useful method to keep weed management under control would be to **adjust the planting density**. This way, the weeds can be controlled more easily by increasing the distance between the trees and by rotating the cultivated area. However, all these adjustments are associated with additional effort and costs. For example, a lower planting density means that fewer trees can be grown in the same area, making the **individual tree more expensive**.

Plant protection

There are problems to regulate certain pests and diseases. For example, for the Green leafhoppers (*Empoasca decedens*) in peach, Psylla (*Cacopsylla pyri*) and Pseudopsylla in Prunus and for aphids in apple and in all prunus. More preventive and frequent applications with non-synthetic PPP are needed. Also, the opening of licenses under EU directives e.g. for Zeolith, Kaolin would help. Against the different pests would help different adaptations depending on the pest, such as trapping, fencing, oil applications, and more intense monitoring. Robust and resistant varieties would of course also be a solution. Another problem is the protection from drift spraying from close conventional farming.

Tree quality

The quality of organic trees is **expected to be as high as conventional trees**. However, this is difficult due to hormones, mineral fertilizers, etc., which are not permitted in organic farming. For example, shoot termination of apples and pears is a big challenge, as **no hormones are allowed** and **branching** is thus **very dependent on the weather conditions** (temperature differences, rainfall, etc.). The **growth** (to get a good tree size within one or two years) also can be difficult with the regulation of organic production (**Absence of mineral fertilizers**, synthetic PPP). Organic production is **more dependent on good soil conditions** since no short-term solutions are available. In addition, it is difficult to produce the **same quality over the years** (concerns all crops).

During the workshop, it became clear that there is a need for **training nursery(wo)men** on how to manage certain cultivars for good quality and to get the material to the right market, especially for new varieties. It should also be shown that **weak but homogenous trees are better** than strong but heterogenous trees and that farmers have different expectations depending on their production (extensive vs. intensive) system. The above-mentioned **differences in tree quality between organic and conventional trees** were also examined. It was concluded that the trees will look the same after two to three years, no matter which production system they have grown with. The only important and decisive factor is **pruning**. In organic farming, the pruning of the tree is very important for its development and requires expertise. A conventional tree, on the other hand, is not so dependent on correct pruning and can develop well even with fertilizer, etc. In the workshop in Frick, it was also stated that there is a **definition of the minimum requirements for organic tree quality only in Switzerland but not on the EU level** and that organic trees are more expensive than conventional ones.

Fertilization

Fertilization is especially important when soil conditions are not so good. **Good preparation, green manure and maintenance of the soil** (organic fertilizer) help here. However, fertilization must be adapted, because organic fertilizer has a slow effect.

Sanitary status of the organic plant material

Within the workshop, great importance was attached to the challenges with the sanitary status of the organic plant material. Also, in the survey, one-third of the nursery (wo)men said that they had difficulties with it. However, it is interesting that these were almost exclusively conventional nurseries from southern countries such as Spain and Italy. Of course, it would be best to use only virus-free and certified material. To achieve this, however, **many regular controls are needed**, such

as observations by the nursery(wo)men, testing in laboratories, and controls by authority. During the workshop, it was discussed whether phytoplasma-free trees are needed at all or whether the CSC level is sufficient. It was also pointed out that, for example, no one tests apple proliferation on trees and that there is no solution for ESFY. So, there are still many open questions in this area. A good start would be, to begin with, virus and phytoplasma-free rootstocks and to keep the nuclear stocks aphid free.

Small numbers of variety + rootstock combinations

Two-fifths of the respondents said they had challenges with small numbers of variety and too many different rootstock combinations. The respondents were both organic and conventional producers, from Southern as well as Northern countries. Possible solutions for this would be to limit oneself to a small number of combinations through feedback from the growers. Furthermore, nurseries already produce only on demand (e.g. two years in advance). For nurseries with a catchment area that covers many different microclimates, a master key rootstock that grows well in all conditions would be beneficial. The choice of the right rootstock seems to be more important in organic farming than in conventional, as shown by the output of the survey (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Importance to choose the right rootstock in organic and conventional farming. 5 = very important; 1 = not important at all.

Outcomes workshop:

In addition to the difficulties that emerged from the survey, others were listed during the workshop:

- (i) Workload
- (ii) Problem of not enough production area (crop rotation) → Trade-off between fully organic and using the same land without crop rotation
- (iii) No organic mother plant stocks → Bottleneck
- (iv) Testing mixed systems – e.g. Agroforestry
- (v) Resilient farming systems for the future
- (vi) Marketing aspects

Conclusions

Breeders

Through the survey, it became clear that breeders see problems mainly in getting adapted parents and pre-breeding material which is more robust material and within the testing of candidate lines (Figure 6). Across the board, however, almost always the same problems are listed in each area. For example, the sanitary status of plant material or the high disease/pest pressure is a recurring problem. Furthermore, a lack of facilities, staff, time, knowledge, and money are some of the biggest difficulties for breeders. National or international funds could solve this, but public collections/funds are rare and if they exist, easy access to them could be a problem. A recurring theme is a participatory approach. Many breeders say that networks could solve various problems. For example, information and genetic/plant material can be exchanged quickly via networks. This means, for example, that not all tests have to be done by one breeder, but can be done in cooperation with others. This saves money, staff, and time and at the same time, the different parties benefit from each other. It was also emphasized during the workshop that the InnOBreed project should have the goal of analysing the existing networks and highlighting which ones should be strengthened or where a network is missing. For example, a chatroom for breeders for quick and easy exchange among each other or an online platform with information on all pests and diseases were mentioned as examples of networking. In such networks, it is also easier to develop and test new methods together, for example, screening methods for climatic change. The climatic change was repeatedly mentioned as one of the biggest influencing factors in all areas. This topic should certainly be given a lot of attention in the future. New screening methods and tools for specific traits which are more important in organic growing systems are still missing and need to be tackled and validated during the InnOBreed project period.

Variety testers

Similar problems as with the breeders were also found within the variety testing. A lack of funding, space, and staff for conducting testing over a long period is a recurring issue. Furthermore, the high pest and disease pressure and the harmonization of data were listed as difficulties. Simpler and faster methods such as digital methods (e.g. image analysis of yield) could save time, staff, and money. The simpler methods can also be carried out by less skilled people. In addition, these methods would be easier to harmonize, as they are not based on the evaluation of different people but on a program that always evaluates in the same way. Other participatory approaches were also mentioned, such as planting directly in orchards from professional producers to save space. The need for non-destructive tools and notation scales fitting for organic production was also mentioned in the survey. When asked about new traits which will become more important for organic production in the future, almost all of the respondents answered "adaptation traits to climate change ". Furthermore, disease and pest susceptibility and long shelf life, and tolerance to storage diseases were often mentioned. To define new testing methods for these traits and to find non-destructive tools, a good network is advantageous. In this way, testers can regularly exchange ideas and develop new ones together.

Nursery(wo)men

The results of the survey showed that weed management (no herbicides) is the biggest difficulty and also the biggest cost factor (Figure 14). This is mainly due to the high working costs of mechanical weed control. Innovations in cultivation methods, such as the use of cover plants, chickens, or adjusting the planting density, can reduce the problem, but at the same time often increase the costs per tree. Furthermore, many struggles with plant protection (no synthetic pesticides allowed) and fertilization (no mineral fertilizers allowed). More preventive and frequent applications with non-synthetic PPP are needed. Also, the opening of licenses under EU directives e.g. for zeolite and kaolin would help. It was also pointed out that, for example, no one tests apple proliferation on trees and that there is no solution for ESFY. So, there are still many open questions on the issue of sanitary status. A good start would be, to begin with, virus and phytoplasma-free rootstocks and to keep the nuclear stocks aphid free. A few of the nursery(wo)men also mentioned that they have challenges with small numbers of variety and rootstock combinations. Others already solve this by only producing on demand (e.g. two years in advance) or only offering a few combinations based on feedback from growers. The choice of the right rootstock seems to be more important in organic farming than in conventional, as shown by the output of the survey. As there is only a definition of the minimum requirements for organic tree quality in Switzerland, but not in the EU, it is difficult to obtain strong, homogeneous organic trees. There is a need for training nurserymen on how to manage certain cultivars for good quality and to get the material to the right market, especially for new varieties. It should also be shown that weak but homogenous trees are better than strong but heterogenous trees and that farmers have different expectations depending on their production (extensive vs. intensive) system. In conclusion, knowledge is an important tool to minimize difficulties and cost factors. This requires good literature, more research, and good dissemination of knowledge.

‘Innovation Providers’

Annex 2 shows the list of stakeholders who belong to the InnOBreed project and moreover it highlights ‘Innovation Providers’ who have been identified due to the survey and who have been defined in D1.1. as people who has enhanced, triggered or implemented an innovative solution in her/his workflow, either as technical innovation or social innovation. They are having strong professional links with innovation, either having facilitated and triggered innovation or developed innovation in organic fruit breeding.

Annex 1: Minutes of the workshop

Integrating traits fitting with climate change

- (i) Timeline of climatic change vs. timeline with breeding programs
- (ii) Need for a dedicated testing network:
- (iii) Which traits should be added?
 - a. Late frost susceptibility
 - i. Simulate frost e.g. in a climate chamber
 - ii. Less information available about these traits
 - iii. Or new varieties are coming from regions in which late frost is not important
- (iv) Low chilling vs. late frost susceptibility and also winter frost
- (v) Need of at least 2 testing networks depending on different climatic regions
- (vi) Selection of “broad” vs. “narrow” adaptation
- (vii) Change of climate in different regions
 - a. Modelling of future conditions
 - b. Define “new regions”
 - c. Include also pests
- (viii) Early involvement of growers from different climatic conditions

Screening methods Stone fruits

- (i) Linked to access valuable information/data → sharing knowledge tools in a participatory approach
- (ii) Especially important regarding climate change
 - a. Chilling requirements are very important, especially in the south, less so in the north → depending on region → different breeding programs needed
 - b. Chilling tolerance
 - c. Late frost especially in the north
 - d. More consequence to climatic change traits in InnOBreed
- (iii) Access to information about screening methods
 - a. Making methods public, already at an early stage: CEP (F), Institute in Murcia (E), CTIFL (with weighing buds and measuring sugar content as an indicator for peach, apricot (and cherry))
 - b. Paper from EUFRIN peach network
 - c. Database with information on traits from varieties
- (iv) Establish easy methods (forcing experiments)
- (v) Not many people can apply specific screening methods
- (vi) To get detailed information about breeding material is sometimes very long → also variety testing is time-consuming
- (vii) Change priorities of important traits that are used for selection? Ideotyping!
- (viii) Traits with plasticity vs. stability
- (ix) two separate networks for stone and pome fruit? Or would you rather separate regions?
- (x) Yield assessment at the early selection stage
- (xi) Missing for Monilia

Screening methods pip fruits

- (i) Network → working together to find solutions
 - a. Define methods and see who might already be using them
 - b. Testing methods and further development of these
 - c. Discussion platform, regular meetings → but it already has many, first clarify who is not in a network and what exactly the needs are → If such networks already exist, our task is to support and disseminate them.
 - d. Achieve something within the project (smaller network) and then disseminate it further.
 - e. Platform on which all diseases and pests are listed and for each problem, there is an A4 sheet on which the screening methods are explained → very simple and very practical. → online discussion 1-2 times a year
 - f. Chat room where you can quickly exchange information if you have problems → needs someone to manage it
- (ii) Problems different in the field and the laboratory
- (iii) Selecting also the tolerance ones not only the resistant ones
- (iv) On which soil we will do the testing? Fertilization, without or low..?
- (v) As simple and efficient as possible, so that you don't spend so much time (everyone is busy).
- (vi) Examples:
 - a. Spread infected seedlings homogenously
 - b. Seedlings in the field with no spraying condition for 3 years – “survival of the fittest”
 - c. Scab – spray inoculation (indoor)
- (vii) Screenings
 - a. Frost tolerance → look at which flowers can withstand more frost or varieties that flower later
 - b. Drought, heat difficult to screen → Drought is a rootstock and young tree problem
 - c. Screening for abiotic stress → if the plants are stressed all the time only a small disease can have a big impact
 - d. Climatic events cannot be simulated, but it would be good for the breeders to know what to look out for when such an event takes place. → List of Climatic events and then what to look out for
 - i. Frost – Flower frost → very important in Greece
 - ii. Sunburn
 - iii. Fruit coloration
 - iv. Leaf heat tolerance
 - v. Watercore → Glassiness
 - vi. Greece → winter is not cold enough, trees cannot rest, do not form functioning flowers, and then there is the frost in spring.
 - e. Storage diseases

Novel traits, which become more important for organic production

- (viii) Field assessments
 - a. Harmonization of data collection and database (s)

- b. Involve farmers in the early stage or later stage?
- c. Quality of data?
- d. Local advisors can work with farmers to get feedback from them
- e. In addition to detailed assessment at research stations we also need assessment on farms with a limited number of information (e.g. productivity, growth habit, pruning...)
- f. Evaluation on multiple sites
- (ix) How to assess climate change relevant traits? (drought stress sensitivity, resilience towards spring frost, sunburn, chilling requirement)
 - a. Modelling à 1st phenotype is needed à physiological reaction to climate impact (example: “Ref.- Population”)
- (x) Testing conditions: Evaluation in non-sprayed conditions, No fertilization
- (xi) Combination of cultivars and rootstocks, site-dependent, growing system dependent
- (xii) On-farm testing for more data
 - a. Quality of data? à adapt the evaluation criteria (simplify), develop a simple App or online survey, let the advisors do the assessments or get the feedback from farmers, getting oral feedback is much easier and yields more than on paper
 - b. Problem: to get the farmers at the right time to the trees
- (xiii) Data centralization and analysis à Harmonisation!
- (xiv) *Drosophila suzukii*: evaluation of yellow color
- (xv) *Monilia*: weather conditions and flowering start à Breeding varieties that are resistant to *Monilia*

Annex 2 : List of stakeholders and ‘Innovation Providers’

Name/organisation	Contact Name	Category / policy area covered	Key stakeholder	Innovation provider	Country
R&D community					
IVIA	Alfons Domigno Gento	Researcher/scientist	yes		Spain (Comunidad Valenciana)
NEIKER Basque Institute for Agricultural Research and Development	Amaia Ortiz / Roberto Ruíz	Researcher/scientist	yes		Spain
Agroscope Wädenswil	Andrea Patocchi	Researcher/scientist	yes	1	Switzerland
Julius-Kühn Institut (JKI)	Andreas Peil	Researcher/scientist	yes	2	Germany
Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques (CRA-W) (Walloon Agricultural Research Centre)	Anne Chandelier	Researcher/scientist			Belgium
Aristotelian University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Agriculture, Forestry and Natural Environment, School of Agriculture(Breeding Laboratory)	Athanasios Mavromatis	Researcher/scientist			Greece
Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques (CRA-W) (Walloon Agricultural Research Centre)	Audrey Pissard	Researcher/scientist		3	Belgium
Università di Bologna	Brunella Morandi	Researcher/scientist			Italy
Public University of Navarra (UPNA)	Carlos Miranda	Researcher/scientist			Spain (Navarra)
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Charles-Eric Durel	Researcher/scientist	yes	4	France
Fructus	Claudia Frick	Researcher/scientist			Switzerland
RI.NO.VA	Claudio Buscaroli	Researcher/scientist	yes		Italy
AIAB	Cristina Micheloni	Researcher/scientist			Italy
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	David Page	Researcher/scientist			France
LTZ Augustenberg (Agricultural Technology Center Augustenberg)	Doris Betz	Researcher/scientist			Germany
Education and Trial Centre for Viti-and Fruiculture Weinsberg (LVWO)	Dr. Franz RUEß	Researcher/scientist			Germany
Regional Service for Agrofood Research and Development (SERIDA)	Enrique Dapena	Researcher/scientist		5	Spain (Asturias)
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France) Angers	François Laurens	Researcher/scientist	yes		France
Pro Specie Rara	Gertrud Burger	Researcher/scientist			Switzerland
FS Silberberg	Gottfried Lafer	Researcher/scientist	yes		Austria
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Henri Duval	Researcher/scientist	yes		France
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Department of Agricultural Development, Agrofood and Management of Natural Resources	Ioannis Doukas	Researcher/scientist			Greece
Institut Agro Montpellier	Jean-Jacques Kelner	Researcher/scientist			France
Service Center Rural Areas Rhineland-Palatinate (DLR)	Jürgen Zimmer	Researcher/scientist			Germany
UdL-IRTA Foundation (Institute of Agri-Food Research and Technology)	Lidia Lozano	Researcher/scientist			Spain (Catalonia)
HBLA Klosterneuburg	Lothar Wurm	Researcher/scientist	yes	6	Austria
FIRAB	Luca Colombo	Researcher/scientist			Italy
Università di Milano	Marco Cirilli	Researcher/scientist			Italy

Name/organisation	Contact Name	Category / policy area covered	Key stakeholder	Innovation provider	Country
Agri-Food Research and Technology Center of Aragón (CITA)	Maria Jose Rubio Cabetas	Researcher/scientist			Spain (Aragón)
Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura (Cicytex) (Center for Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura)	Maria Ramos	Researcher/scientist			Spain (Extremadura)
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Marie-Laure Greil	Researcher/scientist			France
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Marine Delmas	Researcher/scientist	yes		France
UNIVERSITY OF BARI	Marino Palasciano	Researcher/scientist			Italy
IVIA	Marisa Badenes	Researcher/scientist	yes		Spain (Comunidad Valenciana)
Aarhus University, Department of Food Science	Martin Jensen	Researcher/scientist	yes		Denmark
University of Reading	Mattew Ordidge	Researcher/scientist			United Kingdom
Julius-Kühn Institut (JKI)	Mirko SCHUSTER	Researcher/scientist			Germany
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Morgane Roth	Researcher/scientist			France
Università di Pollenzo	Paola Migliorini	Researcher/scientist			Italy
Arboretum Du Vallon de l'Aubonne	Pascal Sigg	Researcher/scientist			Switzerland
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Patrice This	Researcher/scientist			France
Department of Deciduous Fruit Trees Institute of Plant Breeding and Genetic Resources	Pavlina Drogoudi	Researcher/scientist			Greece
Dept. of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Environment School of Agricultural Sciences University of Thessaly, Laboratory of Pomology	Persefoni Maletsika	Researcher/scientist			Greece
FibL Österreich	Peter Meindl	Researcher/scientist			Austria
Agri-Food Research and Technology Center of Aragón (CITA)	Pilar Errea	Researcher/scientist	yes		Spain (Aragón)
Università Politecnica delle Marche	Prof. Davide Neri	Researcher/scientist			Italy
VŠÚO Holovousy	Radek Vávra	Researcher/scientist		7	Czech Republic
Universidade de Santiago de Compostella (USC)	Santiago Pereira	Researcher/scientist			Spain (Galicia)
Competence Centre for Fruit Growing Lake Constanz (KOB)	Sascha Buchleither	Researcher/scientist			Germany
Agroscope Wädenswil	Simone Bühlmann-Schütz	Researcher/scientist			Switzerland
Università di Bologna	Stefano Tartarini	Researcher/scientist			Italy
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Sylvaine Simon	Researcher/scientist	yes		France
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Thierry Lacombe	Researcher/scientist		8	France
University of Copenhagen, Department of Plant and Environmental sciences	Torben Toldam-Andersen	Researcher/scientist	yes	9	Denmark
Station de recherche appliquée fruit et légumes (SUDEXPE) (Fruit and Vegetable Applied Research Station)	Valérie GALLIA	Researcher/scientist			France
Institute of Olive tree, Subtropical crops & Viticulture, Olive Oil Laboratory - Kalamata	Vasilis Gkisakis	Researcher/scientist			Greece
Laimburg	Walter Guerra	Researcher/scientist		10	Italy
IMIDA Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development of Murcia		Researcher/scientist			Spain (Murcia)

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INTIA public company, attached to the Department of Rural Development and Environment of the Government of Navarra		Researcher/scientist			Spain (Navarra)
Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura (Cicytex) (Center for Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura)	Margarita López / María Ramos	Researcher/scientist	yes		Spain (Extremadura)
Fruit conservation					
GEVES (French Variety and Seed Study and Control Group)	Audrey Didier	Researchers/scientists			France
Fruit experimental station La Pugère (Bouches-de-Rhône)	Bernard Florens	Researchers/scientists			France
GEVES (French Variety and Seed Study and Control Group)	Carole Dirwimmer	Researchers/scientists			France
Diversifruits asbl	Cédric Guillaume	Users of FTGR	yes	11	Belgium
State Office for Agriculture, Environment and Rural Areas Schleswig-Holstein	Edelgard Heim	Researchers/scientists			Germany
Arche Noah	Elisabeth Arming	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			Austria
Nonnetit	Erling Frederiksen	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			Denmark
Diversifruits asbl	Eva Velghe	Users of FTGR	yes		Belgium
Evelyne Leterme, works on the preservation and diffusion of the fruit heritage of the South-West of France	Evelyne Leterme	Advisor			France
Diversifruits asbl	Fabrice de Bellefroid	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions	yes		Belgium
Rødning, æblets by	Flemming Jensen	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			Denmark
Chambre d'Agriculture 83 (Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur)	Garance Marcantoni	Researchers/scientists			France
Department of Deciduous Fruit Trees Institute of Plant Breeding and Genetic Resources	Giorgos Pantelidis	Researchers/scientists			Greece
ENRx (Espaces naturels régionaux Hauts-de-France) (Regional natural areas in Upper France)	Guillaume Bruneaux	Users of FTGR			France
Fruit arboretum Olderdissen	Hans-Joachim Bannier	Users of FTGR	yes	12	Germany
Les croqueurs de pommes (Association of amateur volunteers for the preservation of endangered regional fruit varieties)	Henri Fourey	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			France
Rete di Conservazione e Sicurezza ARSIAL (art. 4 L.R. n. 15/2000)	Immacolata Barbagiovanni	Users of FTGR			Italy
Fondazione Archeologia Arborea	Isabella Dalla Ragione	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			Italy
Espaces Naturels Régionaux (ENRx)/Centre Régional de Ressources Génétiques (CRRG)	Jean-Baptiste Rey	Researchers/scientists	yes	13	France
Chambre d'Agriculture 13 (Bouches-de-Rhône)	JM Montagnon	Researchers/scientists			France
Parc naturel régional du Luberon (PNR Luberon)	Julie Rigaux	Users of FTGR			France

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HBLA Klosterneuburg	Karin Silhavy Richter Martina Staples	Researchers/scientists	yes		Austria
Obsortengarten Ohlsdorf	Klaus Strasser	NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			Austria
Pometet	Lasse Lose	Researchers/scientists	yes		Denmark
Olive & Agroecological Production Systems Lab (EOPS), Department of Agriculture - School of Agricultural Sciences, Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU)	Manolis Kampourakis	Researchers/scientists			Greece
Parc naturel régional du Verdon (PNR Verdon)	Marc Doussières	Users of FTGR			France
INRAe (National Institute of Agronomic Research in France)	Marine Delmas	Researchers/scientists			France
Parc naturel régional du Luberon (PNR Luberon)	Mathias Meignan	Users of FTGR			France
3A-PTA	Mauro Gramaccia	Users of FTGR			Italy
Self-employed ethnobotanist	Pauline Mayer	Users of FTGR			France
Esteburg fruit growing Center Jork (Competence center for fruit growing in northern Germany)	Peter Heyne	Users of FTGR		14	Germany
Centre Pomologie Alès (National Pomology Center in Alès en Cévennes)	Sabine Rauzier	Users of FTGR			France
Invenio (Experimental station for the fruit and vegetable sector in New Aquitaine)	Sébastien Cavaignac	Researchers/scientists			France
VZ Haidegg	Thomas Rühmer	Researchers/scientists	yes		Austria
Department of Deciduous Fruit Trees Institute of Plant Breeding and Genetic Resources	Thomas Sotiropoulos	Researchers/scientists		15	Greece
Fruit experimental station La Pugère (Bouches-de-Rhône)	Vincent Lesniack	Researchers/scientists			France
Conservatoire Botanique National Méditerranéen de Porquerolles (National Mediterranean Botanical Conservatory of Porquerolles)		NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			France
Union Pomologique de France		NGO's managing FTGR collections & utilisation's actions			France
French Institute of Vine and Wine (IFV)		Researchers/scientists			France
Organic fruit breeding supply					
Viveros Candamo	Adela Martinez	Regional nursery of local cultivars			Austria
Apofruit	Alberto Aldini	Grower			Austria
Variety Research Institute of Cultivated Plants (V.R.I.C.P.)	Alexandra Chatzigeorgiou	Examination offices (registration)			Austria
WUR	Alma van der Heiden			16	Austria
Union of Ilia Region Ecofarmers	Andreas Varotsos	Short supply chain actors/direct market operators			Spain
ARREU Cooperativa de Agricultura de Montaña	Andreu Vila Pascual	Advisor	yes		Spain
Angelo Vivai	Angelo Cantagalli	Organic nurseries			Spain
Biofarm	Antje Schiffer	Processors			Belgium
Bio Nouvelle Aquitaine	Antoine Dragon	Advisor	yes		France
Bioterra	Antonio Pérez Amaya	Grower			Spain

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Organic Farming Consultance	Aris Gerakis	Advisor			Greece
Benoit Piron	Benoit Piron	Advisor			France
Vesterled frugtplantage, organic and IPM-fruitgrower	Birgitte Agerkov Pedersen	Grower			Denmark
Independent advisor	Carlo Bazzocchi	Advisor			Italy
ALSIA	Carmelo Mennone	cultivar testing for dessert fruits/Authority			Italy
	Carsten Pedersen	Organic breeder			Denmark
Cédric GUILLAUME	Cédric Guillaume	Processors			Belgium
Apofruit	Ceredi Gianni	Grower			Italy
Organic farmer/storekeeper	Christian Vogt	Grower			Switzerland
FEDERATION DES FRUITS ET LEGUMES D'OCCITANIE	Christine Schmitt	Advisor			France
Christophe Delay	Christophe Delay	Organic nurseries			France
GRCETA Basse-Durance	Christophe Mouiren	Advisor			France
Union of Northern Greece Ecofarmers	Chrysa Skorditi	Short supply chain actors/direct market operators			Greece
GAB22	Claire Sallibartan	Advisor	yes		France
LW Kammer Steiermark	Claudia Freiding	Advisor			Germany
Claus-Peter Münch	Claus-Peter Münch	Organic farmer & bundler			Germany
Consejo de la DOP Sidra de Asturias	Daniel Ruiz				Spain
Biofruits SA	David Biselx	Processors			Germany
Agriion	Davide Nari	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			Italy
NOVAFRUITS	Didier Dujardin	Organic breeder		17	France
Dierk Augustin	Dierk Augustin	Organic farmer & bundler			Germany
Chliara farm	Dimitrios Grammatitis	Grower			Greece
Esteburg fruit growing Center Jork (Competence center for fruit growing in northern Germany)	Dr. Hinrich Holthusen	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			Germany
Arbolé	Efrén Martín	Regional organic nursery of local cultivars	yes		Spain
Ministry of Rural Development and Food, Directorate of Quality Schemes and Organic Farming	Eleni Tzavara	Authority			Spain
Evelyne Leterme	Evelyne Leterme	Advisor	yes		France
Research institute of organic agriculture (FiBL)	Fabian Baumgartner	Advisor			Switzerland
Apoconerpo	Faraone Alessia	Grower			Spain
Obstbau Prem (organic)	Fritz Prem	Grower			Germany
Naturitalia	Giacomo Garulli/Cristiano Pilotto	Processors; Fruit storage; wholesalers			Italy
IOANKRAVARITISBIOFARM	Giannis Kravaritis	Grower			Greece
Giorgos Sagris	Giorgos Sagris	Grower			Italy
O.P. ORTOFRUTTICOLA IONICA	Giovanni Ranaldo	Grower			Italy

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ALCENERO	Greta Gubellini	Processors			Italy
Espaces Naturels Régionaux (ENRx)/Centre Régional de Ressources Génétiques (CRRG)	Guillaume BRUNEAUX	Cultivar testing for processing (cider, juice, compote, ...)		18	France
Hortiadvice	Hanne Lindhard	Advisor	yes		Denmark
Organic farmer (cider apple)	Hans Oppikofer	Grower			Germany
Heinrich zum Felde	Heinrich zum Felde	Organic farmer & bundler			Germany
Organic farmer	Hermann Kuppelwieser	Grower			Germany
CETA Cavaillon	Hugues Reynolds	Advisor			France
Agromillora	Ignasi Iglesias	Nursery	yes	19	Italy
ARSIAL (Agenzia Regionale per lo Sviluppo e l'Innovazione dell'Agricoltura del Lazio)	Immacolata Barbagiovanni	Authority			Italy
apfel:gut e.V.	Inde Sattler	Organic breeder		20	Germany
Agricultural Cooperative of Zagora-Pilio	Ioulia Papoulia	Grower			Spain
Espaces Naturels Régionaux (ENRx)/Centre Régional de Ressources Génétiques (CRRG)	Jean-Baptiste REY	Organic breeder			France & Belgium
SOLEBIO	Jean-François BENOIT	Retailers			France & Belgium
Andreigård aps, organic grower	Jeanne Philip	Grower			Denmark
Organic farmer	Jörg Streckeisen	Grower			Denmark
Haciendas Bio	José Ramón Rituerto	Grower			Spain
Bio Nouvelle Aquitaine	JP Gouraud	Advisor			France
Alnarp University (SLU)	Kimmo Rumpunen				Sweeden
Association of Organic Farming Certifiers	Kiriakos Palasidis	Organic certification			Greece
ADV Ecologica de Ponent	Laia Viñas	Advisor			Spain
Westergaards planteskole	Lars Westergaard	Organic nurseries	yes		Denmark
Nurseries Nv Johan Nicolaï	Laura Nicolaï	"IPM" nurseries, "IPM" breeders	yes	21	Belgium
CIVITALIA	Luigi Catalano	Mixed organic/conventional nurseries			Italy
Esteburg fruit growing Center Jork (Competence center for fruit growing in northern Germany)	Madeleine Paap	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits	yes		Germany
Bio Occitanie	Marc Miette	Advisor			France
AGRECOASTUR S. COOP. ASTUR	María Luz García Rodríguez	Organic fruit growing and processing (users of local cultivars)	yes		Spain
CTIFL	Marie Vincent	Advisor			France
Tobi Seeobst	Martin Ammann	Fruit storage			Germany
Biobaumschule Schafnase	Martin Artner	Organic nurseries	yes		Germany
Organic farmer	Mathieu Vouillamoz	Grower			Germany
Organic farmer	Matthias Faeh	Grower			Germany
apfel:gut e.V.	Matthias Ristel	Organic breeder	yes	22	Germany
Michael Krenn	Michael Krenn	Organic breeder	yes		Germany
Baumschule Schafnase	Michael Suanjak	Organic nurseries	yes		Germany

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FARMA U TŘÍ DUBŮ s.r.o.	Michal Kahoun	Cultivar testing for processing (cider, juice, compote, ...)			Greece
Afruex	Miguel Ángel Gómez	Grower			Spain
NewPlant	Mirco Montefiori	"IPM" breeders/ cultivar testing for sessert fruits			Italy
Agrupación de cooperativas Valle del Jerte	Mónica Tierno Díaz	Grower			Spain
Esteburg fruit growing Center Jork (Competence center for fruit growing in northern Germany)	Nadine Klein	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			Germany
ITAB	Natacha Sautereau	Advisor			France
better3fruit (apple and pear breeding)	Nicolas Stevens	"IPM" breeders	yes		Belgium
AGROBIOLOGIKI	Nicolette van der Smissen	Advisor	yes		Greece
Poma Culta	Niklaus Bolliger	Organic breeder		23	Switzerland
POM'EVASION	Olivier MAUGEAIS	Grower			France
Ökoland Vertriebs GmbH, Bio Austria	Otto Kicker	fruit storage, retailer			Germany
Orogel	Pagliarani Michele	Processors			Italy
apfel:gut e.V.	Peter Heyne	Advisor			Germany
Peter Rolker	Peter Rolker	Organic farmer & bundler			Germany
Ovocnářská farma Kareš	Petr Kareš	Grower			Czech Republic
Fördergemeinschaft Ökologischer Obstbau e.V. (FÖKO) (Association for the Promotion of Organic Fruit Growing)	Philipp Haug	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits	yes		Germany
CETA du Vidourle	Philippe Blanc	Advisor	yes		France
Vergers des Pruneraies	Philippe Sfiligoï	Advisor			France
Pierre Marie LADURON	Pierre Marie Laduron	Grower			Belgium
RETE ITALY VARIETY CLUB	Pirola Cosatntino Silvio	Breeder			Italy
Harndrup Frugt	Poul Rytter Larsen	Grower			Denmark
Aegean Islands regional authority administration- Agriculture sector	Rallitsa Tsigkou	Authority			Greece
ASSOCIATION D'ORGANISATION DE PRODUCTEURS PÊCHES ET ABRICOTS DE FRANCE	Raphaël Martinez	Advisor			France
IFPC - Institut Français des Productions Cidricoles	Rémi BAUDUIN	Processors			France
NOVAFRUITS	René Stiévenard	Organic breeder	yes	24	France
NOVAFRUITS	René Stiévenard	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			France
NOVAFRUITS	René Stiévenard	Grower			France
Proef Centrum Fruitteelt (PCF)	Renske Petre	Advisor & Variety testing	yes	25	Belgium
Escola Agrària d'Alfarràs	Rosa Cortes	Advisor			Spain
Glauser's-Bio-Baumschulen	Ruedi Glauser	Organic nurseries			Germany
Agroscope	Samuel Cia	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			Switzerland
Fruttidoro	Samuele Dalmonte	Nursery			Italy
Pépinière Grange	Sébastien Grange	Organic nurseries	yes	26	France
Pépinières Lafond (Lafond nursery)	Serge Lafond	IPM nurseries			France

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Gaiaspirit (network of multifunctional farms)	Sevi Liouza	Short supply chain actors/direct market operators			Spain
BioFru - Organic Fruit Trees	Sevi Liouza	Grower			Spain
Farmhellas	Sofia Kebapidou	IPM nurseries			Greece
GRCETA Basse-Durance	Sophie Hardy	Advisor			France
Baumschule Neckertal GmbH	Stefan Suter	Mixed organic/conventional nurseries			Germany
Independent advisor	Stefano Tellarini	Advisor			Italy
ECOTROPIO Kastoria Ecofarmers' Association	Stefanos Liouzas	Short supply chain actors/direct market operators			Greece
CTCPA Centre technique agroalimentaire	Stéphane GEORGE	Processors			France
Research institute of organic agriculture (FiBL)	Thierry Suard	Advisor			Switzerland
COOP Danmark A/S	Thomas Roland	Retailers			Denmark
Organic farmer	Tina Siegenthaler	Grower			Denmark
Oroge fresco	Vergnani Stefano	Grower			Italy
Laimburg	Walter Guerra	Cultivar testing for dessert fruits			Italy
<u>ADV de Fruita del Baix Llobregat</u>	Xavier Perez	Advisor			Spain (Catalonia)
POMONA FRUITS	Xavier Viladot	Grower			Spain (Pais Vasco)
better3fruit (apple and pear breeding)		"IPM" breeders			Belgium
Organic technical groupe Val de Loire		Advisor			France
Cooperativa Agroecológica de montaña		Grower			Spain
Euskadi Seed Network (Red de Semillas de EUSKADI)					Spain
CAMPOASTUR S. COOP. ASTUR					Spain
BIOBOSCH ORGANICS, SL		Grower			Switzerland
CASADELLA EXPLOTACIONES AGRICOLAS, SL		Grower			Spain
FRUCTICOLA EMPORDA, S.L.		Grower			Spain
GIROPOMA		Grower			Spain
ASKATASUNA COOPERATIVA					Spain
Ramseier Suisse AG (apple juice producer)		Processors			Switzerland
Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques (CRA-W) (Walloon Agricultural Research Centre)	Alain Rondia	Organic breeder	yes	27	Belgium
Apice Pianta	dr. Di Primio	Nursery			Italy
VIGNOLINI Soc. Agr.	Federico Vignolini	Nursery			Italy
Exoticplant Vivaio di Francesco Maule	Francesco Maule	Nursery			Italy
FRAPPETTA Vivai S.S.	Giulio Frappetta	Nursery			Italy
Vivai Battistini	Massimiliano Meneghini	Nursery			Italy
MAZZUCCHI snc Vivai Pianta	Maurizio Mazzucchi	Nursery			Italy
Vivai Fortunato.		Nursery			Italy
Vitroplant		Nursery			Italy
EU policy makers					

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Euroseeds	Amelie Detterbeck	Euroseeds is the voice of the European seed sector, represents the interests of those active in research, breeding, production and marketing of seeds of agricultural, horticultural and ornamental plant species.			Europe
Plants for the Future ETP	Amrit Nanda	European Technology Platform promoting the flow of innovation to the market			Europe
AIAB (Italian Association of Organic Agriculture)	Cristina Micheloni	Control and certification. Organic regulation in Italy.			Italy
IFOAM Organics Europe (European umbrella organisation for organic food and farming)	Eric Gall	organic regulation			Europe
Coldiretti Bio - Association of Organic and Biodynamic Companies of Coldiretti	Francesco Giardina	Control and certification			Italy
Institut National de l'Origine et de la Qualité (INAO) (National Institute of Origin and Quality)	J. Taverne	Control and certification. Organic regulation in France. Responsible for the implementation of French policy on official signs of identification of the origin and quality of agricultural and food products.			France
EU Parliament	Juliette Leroux	organic farming			Europe
Le Conseil général de l'alimentation, de l'agriculture et des espaces ruraux (CGAAER) (The General Council for Food, Agriculture and Rural Areas)	Marie-Lise Molinier	Agriculture regulation. Consulting, expertise, evaluation, audit and inspection.			France
The French ministry of Agriculture and Food (DGAL)	Mariem Omrani	National and European agriculture regulation			France
Federal Office for Agriculture	Markus Hardegger	Genetic Resources			Switzerland
Federal Office for Agriculture	Olivier Félix	Plant protection			Switzerland
Rete Semi Rurali (Rural Seeds Network)	Riccardo Bocci	Association promoting dynamic and collective management of agricultural diversity			Italy
CEJA - European Council of Young Farmers		CEJA is a forum for dialogue between Europe's next generation of farmers and key decision-makers			Europe
TP Organics		European Technology Platform for organic food and farming			Europe

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Assemblée des Régions Européennes Fruitières, Légumières et Horticoles (AREFLH)		Assemblée des Régions Européennes Fruitières, Légumières et Horticoles			France
Dirección General de Industria Alimentaria /Ministerio Agricultura Pesca y Alimentación Gobierno de España		National policies on organic farming			Spain
Comité Aragonés de Agricultura Ecológica (Organic Farming Aragonese Committee)		Control and certification			Spain (Aragón)
Consejo de la producción agraria ecológica del principado de asturias (COPAE)		Control and certification			Spain (Asturias)
Consejo de Agricultura y Alimentación Ecológica de Euskadi		Control and certification			Spain (Basque Country)
Cosell Catalá de la producció agrària ecològica (CCPAE)		Control and certification			Spain (Catalonia)
Direcció General de Agricultura y Ganadería (Junta Extremadura)		Control and certification			Spain (Extremadura)
Consumer citizens' organisation					
Fédération des Parcs naturels de Wallonie (FPNW)	Nicolas Nederlandt	Environmental organisation			Belgium
Forbrugerrådet tænk	Camilla Udsen	Consumer organisation			Denmark
APRIFEL	Delphine Tailliez	Other			France
Koukouli		Consumer organisation			Greece
Bioscoop		Consumer organisation			Greece
Diktio Oikokinotita	Giorgos Kolempas	Citizen organisation			Greece
Agroecology Network Greece	Giorgos Veikontis	Environmental organisation			Greece
SLOWFOOD ITALIA	Francesco Sottile	Consumer organisation			Italy
Fundación Savia	Francisco Casero	Environmental organisation			Spain
Cooperativa integral del Suroeste (ACTYVA)	Gonzalo Palomo	Citizen organisation			Spain
Paisaje, Ecología y Género	Beatriz Fadón				Spain
La Ortiga		Consumer organisation			Spain
La Vera nos alimenta		Citizen organisation			Spain
Red de Municipios por la Agroecología		Other			Spain
Fédération Romande des Consommateurs	Laurianne Altwegg	Consumer organisation			Switzerland
Other stakeholders					
Sociedad Española de Agricultura Ecológica	Aina Calafat	Organic sector representatives	yes		Spain
Collège des Producteurs SOCOPRO	Alain Grifnee	Label organisation			Belgium
BioSad	Radek Vávra	Facilitators of networks			Czech Republic
PØ	Signe Schrøder	Hobby gardeners			Denmark
Organic Denmark	Helge Bülow	Organic sector representatives			Denmark
METIS	Pierre Rivière	Facilitators of networks			France
Star fruits	Jean-Pierre Plail	Licence holder			France

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Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK) -EURISCO	Stephen Weise	Facilitators of networks			Germany
Istituto professionale Ruffilli	Gianmarco venturi	Trainers/schools			Italy
Istituto tecnico agrario Garibaldi/Da Vinci	Simone Romagnoli	Trainers/schools			Italy
Bioversity-ECPGR Programme	Lorenzo Maggioni	Facilitators of networks			Italy
Istituto Tecnico Agrario Giuseppe Garibaldi Roma	Laura D'Alatri	Trainers/schools			Italy
ISTITUTO TECNICO AGRARIO BASILE CARAMIA-GIGANTE	IGNAZIO ZARA	Trainers/schools			Italy
FONDAZIONE ITS AGROALIMENTAREPUGLIA	VITO NICOLA SAVINO-GIUSEPPE MAGGI	Trainers/schools			Italy
Sociedad Española de Agricultura Ecológica	Concha Fabeiros	Organic sector representatives			Spain
Ecovalia	Álvaro Barrera/ Maria Auxiliadora Vecina	Organic sector representatives			Spain
PTAEEX	Maria Ramos García	Organic sector representatives			Spain
Fundecyt-Pctex	Carlos Cabo	IT sector			Spain
Association Vida Sana		Processors			Spain (Catalonia)
VariCom GmbH	Michaël Weber	Label organisations (club cultivars, etc)		28	Switzerland
Biovalais	Karine Contat	Organic sector representatives			Switzerland
Bio Suisse	Sabine Haller	Organic sector representatives			Switzerland